

Management of Information In BIM Models : Open BIM Workflow and Practical Applications

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Abstract

This thesis explores the application of Building Information Modeling (BIM) workflows for quantity take-off (QTO) and cost estimation in the early design phase, with a focus on leveraging open standards, specifically the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) and Information Delivery Specification (IDS). The study concentrates on workflows for defining information requirements, model preparation, and validation. The following tools were utilized: US-BIM.IDSEditor for defining alphanumeric information requirements; Revit for model preparation and IFC Format exportation; BlenderBIM for model validation; and Power BI, Navisworks, Bexel Manager, and IfcOpenShell for quantity take-off, costing, and construction simulation. The research particularly focused on integrating Power BI for QTO and cost estimation, providing a clearer understanding of project outcomes and aiding decision-making. Additionally, Python programming with the IfcOpenShell library was used to automate and demonstrate efficient property querying and perform quantity take-off and cost estimation. The study also explored a Navisworks workflow involving QTO data export to Excel, requiring additional steps to filter relevant information for cost estimation. A Python script

was developed to streamline this process, although construction schedule simulation remained largely manual, potentially introducing errors and inefficiencies. In contrast, the Bexel Manager workflow automated both QTO and cost estimation with minimal manual intervention. A C script stored essential schedule data within the exported IFC model, ensuring compliance with machine-readable specifications. This research offers insights into potential workflows that could significantly enhance cost estimation and scheduling, proving valuable for researchers and practitioners involved in cost estimation.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/NzwwGg528Ns>

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